

PROCEEDINGS M2D2022

**9th International Conference
MECHANICS AND MATERIALS
IN DESIGN**

Editors

**J.F. Silva Gomes
Shaker A. Meguid**

Funchal, 26-30 June 2022

**INEGI-FEUP
(2020)**

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ASSESSMENT OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF NANO COMPOSITES OF MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBES AND POLYVINYL CHLORIDE, POLYETHYLENE, FOAM POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

The concentration dependence of the elastic modulus $E(C)$ in polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n$ + multiwalled carbon nanotubes is represented and can be described by the percolation model with the extremely low percolation “threshold” in the range $0.02 \div 0.1\%$. The elastic modulus E , shear modulus G were measured. Annealing of structure defects bends out of shape the type of internal friction temperature spectrum. At annealing admixtures, vacancies V go out. The results of examinations of the relaxation processes in a crystalline lattice at thermal and ultrasonic processing on the temperature spectrum of internal friction and elastic module of nano composites are presented.

Keywords: nano composite, carbon nanotubes, internal friction, elastic modulus, ultrasound.

INTRODUCTION

The influencing of ultrasonic (US) deformation ϵ_{US} was researched on anelastic and elastic characteristics of nano composites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT). The criterion of structural relaxation is formed: inelastic structural relaxation can be caused only the that defect of structure, the system of symmetry of which below the symmetry of crystal. It does not determine the effect value of relaxation [1,2].

RESULTS

It's showed, that anelastic internal friction (IF) Q^{-1} and elastic modulus E characteristics are essentially depended from morphology of surface layer. The complex elastic module of polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n$, polyethylene $(C_2H_4)_n$, expanded polystyrene C_8H_8 nano composite E^* is equal to the sum of dynamical elastic module $E' = \rho V_{\parallel}^2$ and loss module $E'' = E' \delta$:

$$E^* = E' + E'' = E'(1 + \delta) = \rho V^2(1 + \delta) = \rho V^2(1 + \pi Q^{-1}) = \rho V^2 \left(1 + \alpha \frac{V}{f}\right), \quad (1)$$

where δ – US attenuation logarithmic decrement, ρ - specimen density; $V_{\parallel}$ - quasitransversal US elastic waves velocity, Q^{-1} – internal friction.

$$\frac{E''}{E'} = \delta = \pi Q^{-1} = \alpha \lambda = \alpha \frac{V}{f}, \quad (2)$$

where α – US attenuation coefficient, λ – the US wave length, f – US frequency. The US attenuation logarithmic decrement δ vibrations with amplitude $A = A_0 e^{-\delta x}$ is equal to [1]:

$$\delta = \ln \left(\frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n} \right). \quad (3)$$

The window illustration of data treatment of quasilongitudinal elastic waves velocity measuring $V_{\parallel} = 2469 \pm 10$ m/sec in nanocomposite polyethylene with low density high pressure $(C_2H_4)_n + 0,7\%$ MCNT by impulse-phase method at frequency $f_{\parallel} \approx 1$ MGz is demonstrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 – The data plot illustration of the quasilongitudinal elastic waves velocity measuring $V_{\parallel} = 2469 \pm 10$ m/sec in nano composite of polyethylene with low density high pressure $(C_2H_4)_n + 0,7\%$ multiwalled carbon nanotubes by impulse-phase method at frequency $f_{\parallel} \approx 1$ MGz.

The considerable absolute value of the elastic module $E(C)$ in Figure 2, the shear module $G(C)$ of polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n + MWCNT$ indicates the strong interaction with the maximum at 0.04% of MWCNT.

Fig. 2 – The concentration dependence of the elastic module $E(C)$ of polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n + MWCNT$.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The concentration dependence of the elastic module $E(C)$ in polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n + MWCNT$ can be described by a percolation model with the extremely low percolation “threshold” in the range $0.02 \div 0.1\%$.
2. As the result of the mechanical study the presence of the strong effect between low-density polyethylene $(C_2H_4)_n$, polyvinyl chloride $(C_2H_3Cl)_n$ and multiwalled carbon nanotubes was confirmed.

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